

Impact of Fast Food on Rural children's Health with their Socio Economic Status in Dist. Kotputli-Behror Rajsthan

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Abstract

This study was done to find out the awareness of health hazards of fast foods, consumption pattern of fast food this survey conduct to-going from door to door in rural areas to collect data about the fast food consumption frequency availability and the social economic status of the children. The main objective of this study was to find out about the diseases, obesity and weakness caused by eating fast food in rural area. In this it was also found out whether the children consume fast food to satisfy their hunger or not. From this study it can be found out why children consume fast food. Children consume fast food not to satisfy their hunger but as per their wish. Children whose family's financial condition was weak also consume fast food frequently 10 to 25 days in a month. This shows that eating too much fast food is not related to poverty. Many children were also seen who do not eat home cooked food but consumed fast food. Those who consume fast food repeatedly or continuously during the remaining months, physical weakness obesity and other diseases like stomach ache, tooth decay, tooth ache etc are seen. This study found out that the consumption of fast food, the direct effect of consumption is visible on the health of children.

Key Word – Fast food consumption, dietary fast food, obesity, health hazards

INTRODUCTION:-

A large part of the population in India is malnourished and more than half the population lives in rural areas. In India despite economic development a large proportion of the population is under nourished and more than half of the population resides in rural location. (Anjali.V. 2019).The focus Studies on the impact of fast food on the development of children in rural areas. The relation among the food access consumed and nutritional status and health in developing countries are not well understood. The pattern of the rural areas is changing to consuming food due to the connectivity of the Highways and the city culture.

India's fast-food industry is expanding at the rate of 40% every year. India ranks 10th in the fast food per capita spending figures with 2.1% of expenditure in annual total spending (Ashakiran, 2012).

Children's are prefer fast food such as Pizza, Burger Panipuri, Sandwich etc. These are not determined by nutritional value. It depend on the availability of the fast food in market.

Random sampling by questioner was conducted in some rural areas of Kotputli-Behror district of Rajasthan state.

The purpose of this study was to find out what effect of fast food has on children' Growth. The fast food causes obesity, weakness or any other diseases.

Effects of regular intake of junk food mainly lack of energy, poor concentration, and obesity leading to inferiority complex, depression, heart disease, high cholesterol, and stunted growth premature aging and tooth decay (Chubbier, 2010)

Methodology

This study was conducted on the effect of fast food in the rural area of Kotputli-Behror district of Rajasthan. **The study was done from June 2023 to December 2023 and collect the data of 502 samples between the age group of 3-14 years by door to door was done by questionnaire and self-interview.**

Developing of Tool

A questionnaire was prepared and pretested was applying for the collecting of information about consumption The questionnaire was simple and brief The study was conducted to access reliability and validity to the questionnaire. The self-made questionnaire was developed.

(A)Collecting information- the schedule was used to collect the information on general profile, name, age, education,Weight, family details, family monthly income among 3-14 years children.

(B)Frequent diet intake- Fast food consumption frequency was recorded in terms of intake of Panipuri, Burger Maggi, Pasta Samosa, Kachori, Chips, Kurkure, Namkeen etc.

We collect sample data on the age group of children, their weight and frequency to consuming fast food as average in a month and also collecting the data about their economic behavior to identify the hypothesis of the relation between the consumptions of the fast food and health. We want to identify the availability of fast food according to the population of area and the consumption frequency of the fast food. So conducting the same type of interview form the shop owner of study area we also try to identify the way of consuming fast food other than the retail market and also identifying the distance or availability of fast food from National Highway.

Age	No. of sample	Average Frequency
3	4	13.75
4	19	15.157
5	41	14.487
6	32	14.593
7	34	14.588
8	41	14.292
9	43	12.418
10	64	14.046
11	69	14.028
12	57	11.929
13	55	10.4
14	43	16.302

Table 1- Showing age of sample, No. of Sample and Average Frequency of Consuming Fast Food

	Age	Average Frequency
kids	3-7 YEARS	14.515
Children	8-14 YEARS	13.345

Table 2-Showing the Average frequency of kids and children to consuming fast food.

MONTHLY INCOME	NO. OF FAMILY
0- 10000	130
10000-20000	155
20000-30000	84
30000-40000	38
40000-50000	33
50000-60000	30
60000-70000	18
70000- ABOVE	14
TOTAL	502

Table 3- Showing monthly income of children's family

Fig. Taking Sample data from rural area

DISEASE DATA		
Age	Frequency of sample	Respond to any health issue
3 - 5	64	5
6 - 8	107	14
9 - 11	176	31
12 - 14	155	23
Total	502	73

Table 4- Showing the no. of children respond to health issue by their age

Graph 1-Showing the % of monthly fast food consumption

VAIRABLE	RESPONDED NO. OF SAMPLE
Obesity	7
Health weakness	35
Toothache	12
Stomach pain	12
Headache	11
Indigestion	2
Acidity	8
Eye weakness	15
Skin disease	6
Hairfall/ change haircolor	5
Asthma	1

Table 5-Showing the no. of children who respond to any health issue

Result and Discussion:-

This study it was found that most of the people who consume fast food 10-15 and 20-25 times in a month are suffering from many disease like - Teeth ache, bad breath, stomach ache, obesity and weakness. It was observed that those who consumed less fast food were found to be physically healthier.

This analysis was based on data from 502 children who were residents of rural area most of the all children consume fast food. According to the WHO children scale, in the age group of 3-14 years, approximately 61% of the children with higher age group and 13%of the children with less age group, approximately 12%of the children with child age suffered from the disease.

According to table 1- Sample of age 14 are consuming fast food higher frequency of 16.302 the reason maybe they take pocket money and spend it on mostly on fast food.

According to table 2- The average fast food frequency of children aged 3 to 7 years is 14.515 days and the average fast food frequency of total children aged 8 to 14 years is 13.346 days. Hence the conclusion is that children of 3 to 7 years age is consume more frequently fast food then children of 8 to 14 years of age group.

According to table 3 - As per the data, the monthly income of 502 children families was ascertained which included 0-10000, 10000-20000, 20000-30000, 30000-40000, 40000-50000,

50000-60000, 60000-70000 and 70000 above. We also expressed the number of families keeping this group in mind.

There is no relation to economy with fast food consuming because most of the economically weaker family children most frequent to consuming fast food.

According to table 4- As per the table 4 data all of the 502 children with 3-14 years aged group only 73 children shows health issue.

According to table 5- As per the data define the responded no. of children with their disease most of the children are shows health weakness, eye weakness and toothache

According to Graph data- As per the graph data 39.24 % children consume Panipuri and 18.12% consume Samosa its show these are easily available in rural area.

The reason behind the health issue the lack of the knowledge of cooking food in local vendor they heat edible oil again and again they not only increase the bad cholesterol level but also reduce the good cholesterol level due to this problems like Parkinson's disease heart disease, stroke, cancer, and various liver problems can increase. Reheating the oil makes it carcinogenic. A carcinogen is an agent that causes cancer.

Children skip their lunch to eat fast food is popular among children because it is available in less time, less cost or because it's tastes is better.

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